

Improving Reliability for Cloud-native 5G and Beyond using Network Coding

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Abstract—Retransmission at the Radio Link Control (RLC) layer is the de-facto technique to overcome packet loss at the cost of increased transmission delay in 5G systems. Softwarization of the 5G core and its adoption of cloud-native architecture allows for bringing in more advanced error correction techniques, such as Random Linear Network Coding (RLNC), into 5G systems. RLNC reduces delay and packet loss by proactively generating and sending combinations of original packets at the cost of more computing. We develop RLNC as a plug-in software in OpenAirInterface (OAI) 5G CN and deploy it. Evaluation results in a practical testbed show that RLNC has decreased packet loss while introducing a low delay.

Index Terms—Network coding, OpenAirInterface, 5G, Cloud-native, Reliability, Low-latency

I. INTRODUCTION

In recent years we have witnessed a rapid transition to cloud computing in mobile networks [1], [2]. Specifically, cloud computing brings tremendous advantages to mobile networks, such as reducing costs (e.g., capital and operational expenditures), enabling innovation, and accelerating time-to-market. Toward this goal, Telco operators have embraced cloud computing for both the core and the RAN to form cloud-native 5G and beyond networks.

Cloud computing virtualizes entities such as User Plane Function (UPF) in 5G and beyond networks, thus allowing for deployment on general-purpose servers. Specifically, free5GC [3] is an open-source project that focuses on 5G Core Networks (CNs), whereby all entities in the core can be implemented using Docker containers. To support large-scale deployments of 5G core networks, 5G-Kube [4] further extends free5GC by employing Kubernetes for control plane components in the core. Similarly, Nervion [5] leverages Kubernetes to provide the large-scale deployment of the RAN.

Virtualizing 5G components aims to meet emerging applications' requirements, such as latency and reliability. 5G and beyond networks [6] aim at reliability as an ultimate goal to provide ultra-reliable low latency communication (URLLC). High reliability enables emerging use cases in 5G and beyond networks, such as connected vehicles and remote surgery. However, wireless communication in the RAN has introduced the most critical reliability concern [7]. To tackle this challenge, the RAN has been featured with transmission modes in different layers, such as in the RLC or physical layers.

Fig. 1. The impact of acknowledge mode (AM) on one-way delay (OWD) for video traffic

However, in traditional mobile networks, as components in the RAN are hardware-specific, transmission modes are fixed, thus hindering the ability to improve reliability further. The cloud-native 5G and beyond networks aim to open up the possibilities to facilitate enhancing transmission modes.

In the cloud-native 5G and beyond networks, the RLC layer provides more flexibility to develop transmission modes than other layers, such as the physical layer. The RLC layer consists of two main transmission modes, namely Acknowledged Mode (AM) and Unacknowledged Mode (UM), that either allow retransmission. RLC relies on the AM to perform retransmission regarding packet loss to ensure reliability. Specifically, when receiving feedback on lost packets from User Equipment (UE), gNodeB (gNB) retransmits these packets stored in its retransmission buffer to the UE. We experiment to investigate the performance of the AM under different noise settings in terms of one-way delay (OWD) from the gNB to the UE in the OpenAirInterface platform [8]. Fig. 1 shows that the AM significantly impacts the OWD due to the retransmission. Specifically, the AM under high noise (brown line) introduces much higher OWD than under no noise (green line). Therefore, the AM is ill-suited to support low-latency use cases in 5G and beyond networks, such as haptics or remote surgery.

While the retransmission technique provides reliability, it

also increases the delay [9]. A well-researched mechanism to ensure reliability without adversely impacting delay is Random Linear Network Coding (RLNC) [10]. RLNC is a Forward Error Correction (FEC) [11] mechanism that provides a linear combination between source packets and random coding coefficients to form coded packets. Subsequently, when receiving the encoded packets, a destination can decode them based on the random coding coefficients without requiring additional signaling or coordination between the source and the destination. RLNC provides various variations, such as Fulcrum codes [12], [13], to provide reliable communication networks, thus demonstrating the great potential of RLNC. Especially Sliding Window and Systematic Block Code Random Linear Network Coding (RLNC) perform low packet delay [14], [15] while ensuring reliability.

We propose integrating RLNC in the cloud-native 5G and beyond networks. However, the challenge is integrating RLNC in the 5G System (5GS) seamlessly. We aim to place the network coding elements (encoder and decoder) in the 5GS as an add-on feature without disrupting the current infrastructure and associated protocols of 5G components. Considering the various requirements of current applications and emerging new use cases, we aim to offer a versatile solution that supports different user demands. Thus, our integration solution must be able to apply different network coding protocols to satisfy the requirements of different use cases. Thanks to the integration with RLNC, the UM sends encoded packets from gNB, which are then decoded at UEs. Our proposed approach does not require retransmission in the RLC layer while providing high reliability. Moreover, considering the potential of RLNC, our proposed approach facilitates further research activities (e.g., integrating different RLNC variations) in the cloud-native 5G and beyond networks. We used network coding functions provided by KODO [16] as the RLNC implementation and then deployed them using Docker containers. For the cloud-native 5G network, we used open-source OpenAirInterface [17] to implement both the core and the RAN. Our implementation results show that integrating RLNC increases reliability significantly by achieving nearly no packet loss in the cloud-native 5G network.

II. RELATED WORK

There are different cloud-native 5G platforms in the literature supporting various purposes. Cloud-native architecture can be used to implement and configure 5G mobile core networks [3], [4], [18] which can be further used to deploy 5G Next Generation Core Functions as cloud-native applications that are easily scalable [19]. Similarly, cloud-native RAN emulators [5] have been designed for massive RAN deployment. The cloud-native approach in 5G supports heterogeneous vertical applications [20], mission-critical applications [21], network slicing [22], and other use cases [23].

The integration of Network Coding (NC) has not been done in cloud-native 5GS in previous studies. The number of studies proposing NC in 5GS are few. Authors in [24] proposed linear network coding to improve delay and reliability for

Integrated Access and Backhaul (IAB) networks. NC transmits redundant packets from higher layers as an alternative to the packet retransmission. In the paper [25], network coding schemes integrated in the Fifth Generation (5G) Radio Access Network (RAN) which improve reliability is presented. Their evaluation shows that NC outperforms standard packet duplication. Authors in [10] investigated the 5G new radio architecture and integration of RLNC for future mobile video delivery in 5G. However, all previous works have modeled theoretical frameworks to evaluate the NC on 5GS. None of them have used a 5G emulator or networks to integrate NC. Moreover, all the previous works have proposed NC to be implemented in RAN requiring significant changes in the RAN stack. For instance in [24], the placement of NC in the IAB protocol stack is proposed in two possible positions. 1) Above Backhaul Adaptation Protocol (BAP) layer. 2) Below Packet Data Convergence Protocol (PDCP) layer. These proposals require changes to be done in the source code of the RAN.

III. BACKGROUND

We consider an end-to-end 5G SA (Stand Alone) network architecture, which is expected to support emerging use cases such as smart factories [26]. The 5G SA consists of the CN and the RAN, as shown in Fig. 2. The 5G RAN consists of gNB as the base station in the 5G RAN and New Radio-User Equipment (NR-UE) as users (or subscribers). To enable a better understanding of our approach, we use the simplified 5G CN deployment, but our approach can also be applied to other 5G CN deployments. The simplified 5G CN includes: *i*) Access and Mobility Management Function (AMF) for handling connectivity and mobility of NR-UE over the N1 interface, and control-plane signaling to gNB via the N2 interface, *ii*) Network Repository Function (NRF) for managing registration of 5G network functions (e.g., AMF), *iii*) UPF for transferring user data to RAN and external networks (e.g., Internet) via N3 and N6 interface respectively, *iv*) Session Management Function (SMF) for handling the interaction with the decoupled data plane and managing session context with the UPF via N4 interface. There are two networks in our 5GS; one enables control traffic between 5G components, and other bridges user traffic NR-UE to external networks.

The Radio Link Control (RLC) layer relies on UM to transfer user traffic without requiring retransmission. Specifically, for the downlink, the RLC layer in gNB buffers the data, and generates and adds RLC header. When receiving user traffic from gNB, the RLC layer in NR-UE buffers, reorders, removes RLC header, and reassembles RLC Service Data Units (SDUs). In the UM mode, the RLC layer disables Automatic Repeat Request (ARQ) to avoid retransmission, making the 5GS in UM mode more prone to errors and losses. To avoid any change in the layers of the 5G protocol stack, we apply NC at the application layer to enhance the reliability of UM. Thus, the existing UM operation is unaffected, consequently facilitating the integration of NC into 5GS.

Fig. 2. Basic 5G architecture including the Network Coding elements (Encoder and Decoder)

IV. SYSTEM DESIGN AND IMPLEMENTATION

Our objective is to enhance the reliability of 5GS without modifying the existing 5GS architecture. To achieve this, we include NC in a 5GS as plug-in software to provide flexibility with retransmission disabled. This section describes the system design and implementation of our NC-incorporated 5GS.

A. System Design

We include an encoder and a decoder in our 5GS to allow NC capabilities, as illustrated in Fig. 2. Our goal is to ensure that the integration of NC introduces minimum changes to the existing standard protocol stack of 5G components. Otherwise, the heavy modification of the existing standard protocol stack requires new protocols for the correct communication between the layers, thus making the protocol stack cumbersome and hindering the adoption of our proposed approach. Moreover, since packet losses can occur even in the CN [27], we must provide redundancy before the CN. Fig. 2 shows our proposed approach, whereby we place the encoder that generates coded redundant packets before the UPF. Meanwhile, we place the decoder in the NR-UE that decodes the coded redundant packets to recover any lost original packets. Our approach provides NC as an extension to the existing 5GS architecture. We run the encoder as a Docker container, so network operators can easily create or destroy encoder containers. Meanwhile, the decoder is realized as an application that can be downloaded and installed in (NR-UE). Thus, our proposed design can be expanded to multiple use cases (or multiple users), thus demonstrating its practicality.

The architecture in Fig. 2 consists of multiple sources sending different types of traffic (haptic, audio; and video) to their respective NR-UEs on the left. During these downlink transmissions, original packets go through the encoder. The encoder outputs the coded redundant and the original packets, which are forwarded to the UPF. The UPF sends the original and the coded redundant packets, over the N3 interface to the gNB. The gNB transmits the original and the coded redundant

packets over the air to the NR-UE. The decoder uses coded redundant packets at the NR-UE to recover any lost original packets.

B. Implementation

RAN emulation [5] can allow a seamless transition to evaluation over a testbed or production network. We use the 5G OAI RAN (OAI RF Simulator), 5G OAI UE, and 5G CN deployment provided by OpenAirInterface (OAI) software [8] to implement our system design. Unlike other open-source projects that offer only the CN or the RAN (e.g., srsRAN [28] and Open5GS [18]), OAI supplies an entire platform for the development of cellular systems by offering SA 3GPP-compliant 5G stack implementation of CN, RAN, and UE. We implement all the 5G components as Docker containers. We create two networks as Docker bridges. The first bridge handles the control traffic between 5G components. The second bridge connects the external network to UPF for transferring user data to NR-UE.

The NC protocols, i.e., Sliding Window and Systematic Block Codes, are implemented on top of the KODO library [29] using a Python wrapper. KODO library provides customized solutions [16] such as deriving different coding schemes. The parameters, namely payload size and Galois Field (GF) size, have to be set the same at the encoder and the decoder. This setting allows the decoder to decode coded packets from the encoder. For the Sliding Window's encoder, we need to configure the number of coded redundant packets with a certain number of original packets and the window length for coded redundant packets, which is set for the density of the coded redundant packet. The coded redundant packets will be used to recover lost packets. Meanwhile, only the payload and coding window sizes are set in its decoder. The parameters of the Sliding Window's encoder and decoder must match. For both the encoder and the decoder of the Systematic Block Code protocol, we must set the number of coded redundant packets in a given generation size since these will help recover lost packets.

V. EVALUATION

In this section, we seek the answers to two questions: *i)* Does NC improve the performance of the existing 5GS regarding reliability? and *ii)* How much overhead (i.e., latency) does NC introduce to the existing 5GS?

A. Performance Metrics

We consider packet loss and processing latency that are two important metrics to assess the performance of the 5GS toward URLLC [6].

1) *Packet Loss*: When one or more packets are discarded while in transit, packet loss occurs. In a 5GS, packet loss can occur at the core [27] and RAN (due to its wireless nature). For some 5G use cases, packet loss could lead to lower efficiency, accuracy, and even system failure [30], significantly impacting system reliability. In our measurement, for each test case (audio, video, and haptic), we know the number of packets sent by the respective PCAP file (*sent_pkts*) and count the packets received at the NR-UE container (*rcvd_pkts*). Then the packet loss is calculated as $(sent_pkts - rcvd_pkts) \cdot 100 / sent_pkts$

2) *Processing Latency*: Latency in the network is the time required by a packet to travel from one end to another. RTT typically approximates end-to-end delay, which may be inaccurate due to the asymmetry of pathways causing delay to vary for each path direction [31]. Moreover, real-time applications like multimedia streaming, rely more on the OWD than the RTT [32]. For OWD, we need each packet's sent and received time. We achieve this by modifying tpreplay [33] (our traffic generator) and adding the sending timestamp to the packet payload when each packet is sent. At the NR-UE, we read the sending timestamp of each packet and then compute each packet's OWD by subtracting its sending timestamp from its receiving timestamp.

B. Testbed

Fig. 3. Measurement testbed including encoder, decoder, and 5G components that connect to each other via two overlay networks

Our testbed architecture is illustrated in Fig. 3. It consists of four physical computers and a Gigabit Ethernet network. These four computers provide the processing and storage needed to run the 5G components. Using multiple physical computers to build the testbed provides realistic results, mimicking practical deployments in production environments. Specifically, our testbed setup can be considered for private 5G networks that require small-footprint deployments [34].

1) *Hardware*: We used general-purpose computers with small footprints to build this testbed to imitate the real setup used in real-world environments. All computers come with the same hardware specifications to obtain reliable results. Each computer is configured with an Intel Core i7-6700 (3.40GHz) CPU, 32GB RAM, and two Network Interface Cards (NICs). One NIC is used for the management network, while the other is used for 5G network (i.e., for control and user traffic). All computers run Ubuntu 18.04 (Kernel 4.15.0) as their operating system.

2) *Network*: The 5G network between the computers in our testbed is connected using an Aruba 2930F switch. Specifically, we provide this network for both control traffic and user traffic. The Aruba 2930F comes with Gigabit ports which provide a throughput of up to 112.0 Mpps and a switching capacity of 176 Gbps [35]. The high-performance switching allows to carry both control traffic and user traffic between 5G components. It also supports other capabilities, such as SDN support which make it suitable for virtualized and cloud environments. Moreover, the SDN capabilities can be used for high-mobility use cases that require network flexibility, such as mobile robots in private 5G networks [36].

3) *Software*: Since all 5G components in OAI are deployed using Docker, we installed Docker (version 24.0.1) on all computers to deploy the 5G components. To automate the deployment of 5G components, OAI uses Docker Compose, a tool for deploying multiple Docker containers. Therefore, we used Docker Compose (version 2.17.0) to automate the deployment process. We created two Docker overlay networks to provide 5G network between 5G components deployed using Docker Compose. The two separate overlay networks include: *i)* a control network for signaling traffic between the 5G components, *ii)* and a data network carrying user's traffic from and to NR-UE. In its architecture, the OAI project has adapted to this network setting.

OAI uses the RF simulator [37] to provide a default noise model. According to our observation, this noise model is stable when used with AM mode. However, the UM mode under this noise model is still under development, thus causing unstable results. For this reason, we disable the default noise model and use the iptables as our noise model to create rules for randomly dropping incoming packets at the NR-UE container to analyze the effect of applying NC during realistic packet loss in a 5GS. In wireless networks like 5G, random packet losses can occur due to mobility or sporadic nature of wireless channels [38]. Therefore, similar to other works in 5G networks [38], [39] we also assume random packet loss. We configured the iptables to

have a random packet loss of 10% which has been considered in previous studies [11], [13], [15].

4) *Traffic data*: We used a free and open-source package, *tcpreplay* (version 4.4.2) [33], to generate the traffic needed for the experiments. It allows us to replay captured traffic in PCAP files. To support packet timestamping, we changed the *tcpreplay* source code to make it update the packet timestamp to the current timestamp before sending it. *tcpreplay* is widely used in research and industry and has reliable performance with many configurations for controlling the transmission, such as choosing the network interface and setting the speed limit of transmission [40]. We used various kinds of traffic captured from real content to mimic realistic conditions and outcomes. The types of traffics used in this work are as follows: *i) Audio traffic*: has the highest inter-packet delay (IPD) at 24 ms and a payload size of 480 B (the payload size falls between video and haptic packet size). The PCAP file of this traffic contains 26425 packets. *ii) Haptic traffic*: has a low IPD at 1 ms and has the lowest payload size at 82 B. Meanwhile, the PCAP file contains 635000 packets. *iii) Video traffic*: has variable IPD (from microseconds to tens of milliseconds) and has the highest payload size of 1328 B. This PCAP file sends 11942 packets.

5) *5G deployment*: We deployed each OAI [8] component (latest version) as a single Docker container. The OAI components are then distributed on different physical computers. This separation of components will make the result more realistic than having all components on the same computer and sharing the same resources. All containers are attached to one or both overlay networks mentioned previously in Section V-B3. Note that OAI deploys the external Data Network (ext-DN) container to represent the external network from where traffic is generated. To evaluate NC, we replace the ext-DN container with the encoder container. To direct the user's traffic from the encoder container to the UPF, we configure the IP address of the encoder container to be in the same network as that of the UPF in the Docker Compose file. The encoder Docker image is a Ubuntu system consisting of the KODO-based encoding application. The decoder application is deployed to the NR-UE container by creating a new Docker image where the KODO library is added in the NR-UE Dockerfile provided by OAI. Our proposed design provides flexibility in providing different deployment options for NC elements. For instance, if NR-UE is a laptop or PC with CPU processors, the decoder can also be deployed as a Docker container. As shown in Fig. 3, for OWD measurement, we deployed the ext-DN, encoder, and NR-UE containers on the same physical computer to prevent having different timestamps on each container. This setup ensures we have accurate calculations, specifically the delay calculation.

6) *Measurement process*: Our objective is to investigate the performance of NC in a 5GS without retransmissions. Therefore, we configure the gNB to be in UM mode and set the number of Hybrid Automatic Repeat Request (HARQ) rounds to 1 so there is no retransmission at both RLC and MAC layers.. The measurement process is based on the data flow

in the user plane of the 5GS. We examine two measurement scenarios- 1) 5GS with NC and 2) 5GS without NC. For the first scenario, *tcpreplay* is used in the encoder container to generate traffic by running one of the PCAP files mentioned earlier. The generated traffic is first processed by the encoding operation running in the container, which produces redundant coded packets and the original traffic. The resulting traffic will go through the 5G user plane, including UPF and gNB containers, until it reaches the NR-UE container. The noise model (based on the iptables) in the NR-UE container will apply random packet loss before the decoder application receives the traffic. The decoder will decode the traffic and recover the original traffic (if lost). In the second scenario, *tcpreplay* uses one of the PCAP files to generate traffic in the ext-DN container. However, the original traffic is not processed by any NC element and reaches the NR-UE container. Each scenario mentioned above is performed ten times for every PCAP traffic (audio, video, and haptic) because the obtained confidence intervals were already significantly small.

C. Studied Schemes

We implement two NC schemes in the 5GS:

- Sliding Window (SW) RLNC: is an NC scheme where redundant coded packets are spread in between small sets of source packets. In our testbed, SW's encoder sends eight coded redundant packets after every 16 original packets, and the window size for coded redundant packets is set as 16. For its decoder, we only have to set the coding window size as set in its encoder.
- Systematic Block Code (SBC): is an NC scheme in which a block of uncoded packets is transmitted first, followed by redundant coded packets [15]. For both its encoder and decoder, the number of coded redundant packets is set as either 8 or 32 with generation size=64.

The encoder and decoder of SW and SBC have a high field size of $GF(2^8)$, while the payload size is fixed as per the traffic. Thus, the payload size parameter is fixed as 1328 B, 480 B, and 82 B receptively for our video, audio and haptic traffic.

D. Performance Results

1) *Packet loss*: We aim to examine whether NC can improve the reliability of 5GS (in UM). Toward this aim, we investigate packet loss under different types of traffic. In the pure UM case (no NC), a packet loss of 10% is consistent with the loss configured in iptables for all traffic. The results in Fig. 5 show that the packet loss of the pure UM is much higher than the NC schemes. We also observe from Fig. 5 that SBC ($r = 8$), while having packet loss lower than pure UM, is still higher than other NC protocols. This indicates that redundancy of 8 packets is insufficient to fully recover the 10% packet loss. We found the redundancy of 32 packets for SBC to have optimum packet loss performance. The better performance of SBC ($r = 32$) over SBC ($r = 8$) is due to the fourfold increase in redundant packets. For a fair comparison, SW is also configured to send around 32 coded redundant

Fig. 4. OWD measurements in downlink for (a) video, (b) audio, and (c) haptic packet.

Fig. 5. Packet loss measurement under different types of traffic

packets, similar to SBC ($r = 32$). We can observe from Fig. 5 that SW and SBC ($r = 32$) achieve similar performance in terms of packet loss. SW and SBC ($r = 32$) reduce the packet loss from 10% to almost 0% in haptic and audio traffic. They send 32 redundant coded packets with every 64 original packets, enough to recover the lost 10% audio and haptic packets. Compared to audio and haptic traffic, video traffic has variable and low IPD, where almost 43% of the video packets have IPD in microseconds, of which around 18% are less than $100 \mu s$. Consequently, the encoder and the decoder must rapidly process the video packets. Fig. 5 shows that SW reduces the packet loss to 0.95% while SBC ($r = 32$) reduces to 1.45% for the video traffic. The packet loss incurred with NC for the video traffic is minor and thus tolerable for various video applications like live streaming.

As expected, applying NC to the 5GS significantly decreases the packet loss, thus increasing the reliability of the 5GS. Specifically, both SBC and SW reduce the packet loss for video, audio, and haptic traffic compared to pure UM. The amount of packet loss reduced depends on the NC protocol and its parameters. For instance, a protocol with fewer redundant coded packets, as in the case of SBC ($r = 8$), produces lower packet loss than pure UM but not as low as SBC ($r = 32$). Considering the growth of hardware capability (e.g.,

processing millions of packets per second [41]), it is reasonable for SBC ($r = 32$) to send more redundant packets.

2) *OWD*: Many applications have strict delay requirements, so we aim to increase reliability while having low delay side effects. Thus, it is important to analyze how much extra delay is added to the existing 5GS by using NC. We evaluate OWD for different types of traffic. The containers are run on separate hardware reducing the competition for computing resources. Thus, the OWD plots for SBC when $r = 32$ and $r = 8$ are not significantly different because the NC protocol is the same, while the only difference is the number of redundant packets for which the processing time is not notably distinct. Therefore, in this subsection, we only describe SBC when $r = 32$. As can be observed from Fig. 4, pure UM incurs the least OWD among the studied schemes. As shown in Fig. 4(a), due to video traffic's low IPD, the queue is built up for the pure UM, which reflects in the high OWD and obtains almost all received packets within 180ms. Meanwhile, SW and SBC ($r = 32$) can recover almost all original packets within 240ms and 340ms, respectively. For the audio traffic, we can observe from Fig. 4(b) that the OWD of NC schemes is higher than the pure UM because of the high IPD (24 ms). For the NC schemes, since the redundant packets are sent after a set of original packets at the encoder, the higher IPD results in more time to recover packets, i.e., to recover original packets, the decoder has to wait for redundant packets to arrive. Specifically, Fig. 4(b) shows that the pure UM gets almost all received packets within 40 ms, while SW and SBC ($r = 32$) take within 370 ms and 1550 ms, respectively, to recover almost all the audio packets. For the haptic traffic (IPD = 1 ms), Fig. 4(c) shows that SW can recover almost all haptic packets within 24 ms while the pure UM gets almost all received packets (excluding lost packets) within 10 ms. SBC ($r = 32$) recovers 98% of haptic data within 80 ms.

We expected that implementing NC would introduce additional delay in the 5GS to encode and decode packets which should not be detrimental to 5G applications. We meet our expectations since we can observe that the delay from NC protocol (such as SW) for video, audio, and haptic traffic is not significantly higher than the pure UM scenario. Considering these different types of traffic, the OWD with NC can satisfy

the latency constraints of various applications, such as intelligent navigation systems (100 ms), augmented reality (100 ms), telemedicine (250 ms), and 4K live video (500 ms) [42]. Therefore, NC can improve reliability without introducing a significant delay in the 5GS.

VI. CONCLUSION

Open-source and adopting cloud-native architecture allow 5G systems to integrate advanced error correction techniques, such as RLNC. We have implemented and deployed two variations of RLNC schemes, Sliding Window and System Block Code, on the OpenAirInterface 5G system as Docker containers. We evaluated these RLNC schemes over different types of traffic, namely audio, video and haptic, in the 5G system. The evaluation results show that RLNC improves 5G's reliability in the UM mode by attaining almost no packet loss at the cost of the additional delay required for encoding and decoding packets. However, this extra delay is not high enough to negatively impact the one-way delay requirements of most real-time applications. Furthermore, our integration of network coding in the 5G system supports the implementation of different network coding protocols that can serve various use cases.

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